

1 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ through Correlative Operando X-ray Diffraction and
2 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

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10 ABSTRACT

11 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, a high-voltage positive Na-ion electrode material, is thoroughly
12 analyzed by coupling operando X-ray diffraction (XRD) and electrochemical impedance
13 spectroscopy (EIS) measurements. $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ follows a complex structural
14 evolution upon electrochemical cycling four consecutive biphasic reactions followed by
15 a single-phase process at the end of the charge. The coupling of XRD and EIS techniques
16 allows the correlation between the phase transformation sequence and transport
17 properties so as to unlock the factors governing the electrochemical performance of
18 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

19 INTRODUCTION

20 Rechargeable Na-ion batteries (NIBs) are becoming one of the most attractive low-cost
21 energy storage alternatives to Li-ion batteries (LIBs) for large-scale stationary
22 applications owing to the almost infinite and even distribution of Na in the Earth crust
23 and the possibility to use Al current collectors for both electrodes.¹⁻³ NIBs, however, still
24 face many challenges, especially in terms of durability. Understanding the evolution of
25 structure and transport properties upon cycling is essential to design materials that can
26 drive NIBs toward a competitive technology for real applications.

27 A variety of inorganic compounds have been investigated as positive electrodes for NIBs
28 such as polyanionic compounds, layered oxides, and Prussian blue and analogue
29 materials (see refs 4-6 for a detailed overview). Polyanionic compounds, which include
30 phosphates, pyrophosphates, fluorophosphates, sulphates, and combinations of these,
31 are particularly interesting as their 3D network provides the required structural
32 stability.^{4,7-9} A well-known polyanionic compound is the olivine-type NaFePO_4 that is
33 analogous to commercial LiFePO_4 for LIBs. NaFePO_4 operates around 2.8 V vs Na^+/Na
34 and exhibits a high theoretical specific capacity (154 mA h/g).^{10,11} Pyrophosphates like
35 $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$,¹²⁻¹⁴ $\text{Na}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$,^{15,16} or $\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$ ^{17,18} have been reported to exhibit the TM
36 $^{3+}/\text{TM}^{2+}$ plateau around 3.0 V vs Na^+/Na (TM = transition metal). However, the heavy
37 $(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$ anion represents a capacity penalty with respect to $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$, leading to a
38 theoretical capacity around 100 mA h/g. An interesting strategy to increase both the
39 capacity and the voltage of these materials is to combine phosphate and pyrophosphate
40 groups giving rise to compounds with general formula $\text{Na}_4\text{TM}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (TM = Fe,¹⁹⁻²¹
41 Mn,²² Ni,^{23,24} and Co).²⁵⁻²⁷ Such formulations compensate, to an extent, the lower
42 capacity of these materials compared to pure pyrophosphates. Additionally, comparable
43 energy density to layered oxides can be obtained,^{25,28} with excellent cycle stability owing
44 to relatively small volume changes during cycling.²⁹ Moreover, these $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ and $(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$

45 mixed polyanionic compounds exhibit Na^+ diffusion coefficients on the order of 10^{-10} to
46 10^{-11} cm^2/s with a low activation energy; therefore, they are excellent candidates as
47 positive electrodes for high C-rate NIB applications.²⁹

48 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ is particularly interesting because it exhibits a high Na^+
49 deintercalation/intercalation voltage (4.5 V vs Na^+/Na) and a good theoretical capacity
50 of 127 mA h/g,²⁵ with 95 mA h/g experimentally obtained at 0.2C and negligible capacity
51 fading after 100 cycles. These excellent properties make $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ one of the
52 most promising Na-ion cathode materials, being its high cobalt content its main
53 drawback. Indeed, research efforts to diminish the cobalt amount in this and other
54 materials are being performed,^{26,30} as well to develop cost-effective recycling
55 processes.^{31,32}

56 The structural evolution of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ upon electrochemical cycling has not been
57 studied yet, although remarkable differences have been observed between isostructural
58 $\text{Na}_4\text{TM}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (TM = Fe,²⁰ Mn²² and Ni)²⁴ compounds. Remarkably, despite all the
59 phase transitions that can be expected from its voltammetry curve,²⁵ $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$
60 still delivers a reversible capacity of 80 mA h/g at very high current densities (4.25 A/g,
61 25 C) and is thus a very good candidate for high-power applications.

62 In this work, the structural mechanism upon electrochemical cycling of
63 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ has been investigated by operando X-ray diffraction (XRD) coupled to
64 electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in order to achieve a correlative picture
65 of the phase transformations occurring upon cycling and their impact on
66 electrochemical properties.

67 2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

68 2.1. Synthesis of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ was synthesized by a sol-gel
69 method.²⁵ $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (Alfa Aesar, 98%), $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Co}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 98%) and
70 $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%) precursors were added stoichiometrically in a diluted
71 HNO_3 solution in the proportion of 3 mol of HNO_3 per mol of Co and Na. Once the
72 precursors were dissolved in the acidic medium, ethylene glycol (EG) was added in a
73 ratio of 3/4 mol of EG per mol of HNO_3 . The liquid solution was stirred and heated up to
74 80 °C for 12 h until a gel was obtained. The gel was heated up to 300 °C for 3 h and the
75 obtained powder was compressed in pellets and annealed at 700 °C for 50 h in air. The
76 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ powder (from hereon referred to as noncoated sample NCP) was
77 mixed with carbon black performance (CBP, Cabot Corporation) in a weight ratio of 5:1
78 and pyrolyzed at 700 °C for 5 h under Ar atmosphere (from hereon referred to as NCP-
79 C).

80 2.2. Structural and Morphological Characterization of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. Powder XRD
81 (PXRD) data were recorded on a Bruker Discover D8 instrument equipped with a
82 LYNXEYE-XE detector (monochromatic Cu radiation $\text{K}\alpha_1 = 1.5406$ Å) and step size of
83 0.02°. Structural models with PXRD datasets were Rietveld refined with the FullProf
84 software³³ and the peak shapes were modeled with pseudo-Voigt functions. The
85 morphology and particle size were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM-
86 Quanta 200 FEG-FEI model) operated at 30 kV. The C-coating was characterized by
87 thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-STA 449 F3 system-Netzch) to quantify the amount of
88 carbon and by transmission electronic microscopy (TEM-FEI Tecnai G2) to observe the

89 homogeneity of the coating. Prior to TEM analysis, the sample was dispersed in acetone
90 and placed onto a holey carbon film.

91 2.3. Electrochemical Characterization of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. The electrodes were
92 prepared by mixing 90% active material with 5% carbon Super C65 (Timcal) and 5%
93 polyvinylidene fluoride (Solef) in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (Sigma-Aldrich). The slurry was
94 cast on a battery grade Al foil. Laminates were dried under vacuum overnight at 120 °C.
95 Disk electrodes (12 mm) were punched and pressed at 4 tons before assembling half-
96 cells in an Ar glovebox (H_2O and $\text{O}_2 < 0.1$ ppm). The performance was tested in coin-type
97 cells (CR2032) vs metallic Na disk, using glass fiber (Whatman GF D 55) as the separator
98 and 1 M NaPF_6 in ethylene carbonate/diethyl carbonate (EC/DEC) as the electrolyte. The
99 galvanostatic measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Maccor
100 battery tester in the voltage window of 3.0–4.7 V vs Na^+/Na at 0.1 C rate (1 C = 127 mA
101 h/g, corresponds to three exchanged electrons).

102 2.4. Correlative Operando XRD and EIS of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. Operando XRD
103 measurements were performed on a homemade electrochemical cell. The XRD
104 experiment was carried out on a Bruker D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer with Cu
105 radiation ($K\alpha_1 = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$ and $K\alpha_2 = 1.5444 \text{ \AA}$) while EIS data were recovered with a
106 VMP3 potentiostat (Bio-Logic). The homemade cell was assembled with 62 mg of NCP-
107 C mixed with 20% Super C65 (Timcal) carbon and 1 M NaPF_6 EC/DEC was used as the
108 electrolyte. The XRD and EIS data were collected in the voltage window of 4.0–4.7 V vs
109 Na^+/Na (the first plateau appears at 4.29 V and the last one at 4.65 V) every 30 mV. Each
110 XRD scan was recovered between $9^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 17.5^\circ$ while EIS was carried out in the
111 frequency range of 5 mHz to 100 kHz, by controlling the electrode potential through the
112 potentiostatic intermittent titration technique with a sinusoidal perturbation of 5 mV.
113 Structural models with XRD data were refined using the Le Bail method with the FullProf
114 software³³ while EIS data were fitted using the Boukamp's equivalent circuit software.³⁴
115 The equivalent circuit included the following parameters: (i) R_{elec} (electrolyte resistance)
116 and R_{SPI} and C_{SPI} corresponding to the resistance and capacitance of the electrode/
117 electrolyte interphase, respectively, (named as the Solid Permeable Interphase-SPI; also
118 known as Solid Electrolyte Interphase-SEI) at high frequency (HF); (ii) R_{CT} (charge-
119 transfer resistance) and C_{DL} (double layer capacitance) at medium frequency (MF) and
120 (iii) Z_w (Warburg diffusion) at low frequency (LF). It should be mentioned that because
121 of the particle surface morphology C_{SPI} , C_{DL} , and Z_w were replaced by a constant phase
122 element in order to take into account any surface inhomogeneity.³⁵

123 2.5. Synchrotron XRD of $\text{Na}_{4-x}\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 < x < 3$). Synchrotron XRD (HRXRD) data
124 were collected on the powder diffraction beamline at the Australian Synchrotron with a
125 wavelength $\lambda = 0.688077 \text{ \AA}$, determined using the NIST 660b LaB6 standard reference
126 material. Synchrotron data were used to determine the Na occupancy at the charged
127 state (4.67 V vs Na^+/Na) by Rietveld analysis. To do so, a coin-type cell with a Kapton
128 window was used and the HRXRD data were obtained in transmission geometry, with
129 an acquisition time of 2.4 min. The electrode was prepared with 3.3 mg of NCP-C and
130 charged to 4.7 V vs Na^+/Na at 40 mA/g (~0.3C).

131 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

132 3.1. Structural and Morphological Characterization of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. The structural
133 model of NCP with PXRD data has been refined by the Rietveld method (Figure 1a) using

134 starting parameters from PDF file 01-089-0579. All reflections correspond to
135 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ which crystallizes in an orthorhombic noncentrosymmetric space
136 group, $Pn21a$. Its crystal structure has polyhedral connectivity and produces large 3D
137 tunnels along the three main crystallographic directions, [100], [010], and [001]. Na^+ are
138 accommodated within these tunnels, where there are four symmetrically
139 distinguishable Na sites (inset Figure 1a).^{36,37}

140
141 Figure 1. Rietveld refined fit of the $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ structural model with PXRD data: (a) noncoated NCP and (b) C-
142 coated NCP. Observed (red points), calculated (black line), differences (blue line), and Bragg reflection (green vertical
143 bars). Inset: unit cell of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ along the c axis showing four distinct Na sites (green for Na, red for O, purple
144 for Co, and pink for P).
145

146 The obtained cell and atomic parameters, Tables S1 and S2, respectively, are in
147 agreement with previously reported data.³⁶ The PXRD pattern of NCP-C (Figure 1b) is
148 practically identical to that of the NCP, indicating that, as expected, the extra heat
149 treatment to C-coat the material does not have any effect on the structure of the
150 material. The final carbon content was found to be 14 wt %, determined by TGA (Figure
151 S1).

152 SEM images of NCP and NCP-C are shown in Figure 2. NCP is composed of large
153 agglomerates of micrometric particles, with a heterogeneous size distribution ranging
154 from 2 to 10 μm . Interestingly, the NCP-C particles are surrounded by carbon nanotubes
155 (CNTs) instead of a carbon layer. Note that the employed carbon precursor does not
156 exhibit nanotube morphology as confirmed by the TEM image shown in Figure 2c.
157 However, NCP-C particles show that there are CNTs as well as carbon nanospheres
158 surrounding the active particles (for more details see Figure S2). Both spherical carbon
159 and CNTs create a conductive percolation network that is expected to enhance the
160 electronic conductivity of NCP and hence improve the electrochemical properties as
161 shown in Figure S3c.

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Figure 2. SEM images of (a) noncoated NCP and (b) carbon-coated NCP-C samples. (c) TEM images of carbon precursor CBP.

165 3.2. Electrochemical Characterization of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. Charge/discharge profiles
166 corresponding to the first two cycles of NCP-C are shown in Figure 3a and the evolution
167 of the capacity upon electrochemical cycling is shown in Figure 3b. The material delivers
168 a stable reversible capacity of 70 mA h/g after 100 cycles, similar to an earlier report,²⁵
169 with excellent capacity retention of above 95% after a few cycles. Na^+ deintercalation
170 occurs throughout several reversible multistep redox plateaux, the first starting at 4.29
171 V vs Na^+/Na and followed by six more, the last one at 4.65 V vs Na^+/Na (for more details
172 see Figure 4). This results in an average voltage of 4.5 V vs Na^+/Na and corresponds to
173 the complete oxidation of all three Co^{2+} atoms to Co^{3+} . The treatment with carbon is
174 essential to improve electron transport, as NCP exhibits very poor electrochemical
175 properties (Figure S3). The NCP-C sample shows higher irreversible capacity in the first
176 cycles compared to NCP but after further cycling Coulombic efficiency is close to 99%.

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Figure 3. Electrochemical properties of NCP-C at 0.1 C rate. (a) Voltage vs capacity curves of the first and second cycles. (b) Charge/ discharge capacity evolution upon electrochemical cycling.

181 The higher irreversible capacity of NCP-C is related to the higher specific surface area of
182 CNTs and electrolyte decomposition reactions because of the high working voltage.
183 Nevertheless, the capacity retention of the material is excellent because of the compact
184 and stable $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ and $(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$ 3D framework. The Co-based structure shows higher
185 capacity retention than isostructural Fe- and Mn-based compounds.^{20,22} The Mn-based
186 structure loses capacity because of the Jahn–Teller distortion while the Fe-based
187 structure shows large polarization at the end of the charge process, which has been
188 attributed to local distortions that affect Na^+ diffusion.

189 3.3. Operando XRD and EIS of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. Although the structural evolution of
190 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ has not been reported yet, a complex mechanism is expected because
191 of the multi-plateaux observed in the galvanostatic curve (Figure 3a). Density functional
192 theory (DFT) calculations have been performed assuming that three crystallographically
193 different Na^+ atoms are fully deintercalated sequentially (Na_2 , Na_3 , and finally Na_4 at
194 4.05, 4.17, and 4.35 V, respectively, while Na_1 would remain in the structure; see inset
195 of Figure 1a for the assignment of Na positions), not considering the possibility of partial
196 Na occupancies.³⁸ Experimentally, the dQ/dV (total differential capacity) curve (see
197 Figure S4) provides more than three-steps for Na^+ deintercalation suggesting that Na^+
198 sites are not completely emptied at each step. Moreover, although Fe-, Mn-, and Ni-
199 compounds are isostructural, their reported reaction mechanisms are completely
200 different. The Fe- and Ni-based compounds operate through a solid-solution reaction.
201 The Fe-based compound still maintains 0.5 Na_3 and 0.5 Na_4 in the structure at the
202 charged state,^{20,39} while for the Ni-based structure 0.75 Na_2 and 0.72 Na_3 are left.²⁴ The
203 Mn-based compound shows several biphasic regions, where 0.25 Na_1 , 0.25 Na_3 , and 0.5
204 Na_4 remain.²² The Na^+ deintercalation sequence of Fe- and Mn-based compounds have
205 been calculated by DFT calculations assuming that 3 Na^+ are removed, while Ni-based
206 compound shows experimentally only 2.53 Na^+ removal. These discrepancies, despite
207 the same initial crystal structure, are indicative of the impact of TM in the Na^+ extraction
208 mechanism and the kinetics of the processes.

209 Figure 4 shows the corresponding operando XRD patterns (4a for the charge and 4b for
210 the discharge processes), the resultant dQ/dV curves, the amount of Na reacted, and
211 the evolution of the phase transitions. The evolution of the cell parameters obtained
212 from Le Bail refinements of all phases are illustrated in Figure 5, together with the
213 resistance values obtained from the fit of the corresponding EIS data. The cell volume
214 evolution of all phases is illustrated in Figure S5 and as expected, the volume decreases
215 as the Na is removed and the opposite trend is observed during Na^+ intercalation.

216

217 Figure 4. Correlative operando XRD and EIS data of the NCP-C sample. XRD patterns collected between $9.0 \leq 2\theta \leq$
 218 17.5° during the first (a) charge and (b) discharge processes with the corresponding dQ/dV (total differential capacity)
 219 and Na concentration evolution (note that SPI layer forms hence Na concentration is indicative). The vertical bar on
 220 the right-hand side shows the evolution of the phase transitions. Because XRD and EIS techniques have been carried
 221 out simultaneously, the measurement time was synchronized for both techniques and thus XRD data were not
 222 necessarily collected at the maximum voltage of the redox peaks.

223 At the beginning of the charge process, all peaks corresponding to the pristine material
 224 (α phase with $a = 18.047(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.524(1) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.510(2) \text{ \AA}$ and $Pn21a$ space group)
 225 slightly shift to higher 2θ values until 4.31 V vs Na^+/Na . At this voltage, the β phase
 226 appears (first oxidation peak in the dQ/dV), and both α and β phases coexist up to 4.39
 227 V vs Na^+/Na . The (200), (210), and (002) peaks of the β phase appear at higher 2θ values
 228 with respect to the α phase, while (011) reflection appears at lower 2θ angle resulting
 229 from the contraction of a and c and the expansion of b cell parameters ($a = 17.257(1) \text{ \AA}$,
 230 $b = 6.646(1) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.484(1) \text{ \AA}$; see Figure 5). The cell parameters of both phases remain
 231 constant, as expected from a two-phase reaction (Gibbs phase rule), up to 4.40 V vs
 232 Na^+/Na (second oxidation peak) where the α phase completely transforms to the β
 233 phase and the new γ phase appears, which coexists with the β phase until 4.48 V (third
 234 oxidation peak). The (011), (210), and (002) peaks of the γ phase appear at even larger
 235 2θ values, while the (200) reflection shifts to a lower 2θ value ($a = 17.437(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b =$
 236 Na^+/Na (corresponding to the fourth oxidation peak) the γ and a new δ phase can be
 237 detected. The new δ phase shows the (011), (210), and (002) peaks at even higher 2θ
 238 values while the (200) is slightly shifted toward smaller 2θ values ($a = 17.419(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b =$
 239 $6.423(1) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.568(1) \text{ \AA}$). At 4.59 V vs Na^+/Na (fifth redox peak), the γ phase has been

240 completely transformed to the δ phase and the ϵ phase appears, which has (011), (210),
 241 and (002) peaks at higher 2θ values than the δ phase. At the end of the charge process,
 242 only the ϵ phase is observed, whose cell parameters continuously evolve as more Na^+ is
 243 deintercalated following a solid-solution mechanism until 4.7 V vs Na^+/Na (4.61–4.7 V,
 244 corresponding to the last oxidation peaks). The refined cell parameters of this ϵ phase
 245 are $a = 17.433(2)$ Å, $b = 6.193(1)$ Å, and $c = 10.344(1)$ Å at the charged state.

246
 247 Figure 5. Evolution of (a) a, (b) b and (c) c cell parameters and (d) resistance values (R_{elec} -red, R_{SPI} -blue and R_{CT} -black
 248 markers) during the first cycle of NCP-C.

249 The multiple-redox plateaux and the formation of several biphasic regions could be
 250 indicative of the occurrence of specific Na^+ /vacancy ordering schemes, as occurs with
 251 the Fe-, Ni- and Mn-based compounds.^{20,22,24} In order to achieve further insight into the
 252 reaction mechanism, the synchrotron diffraction pattern of the oxidized material was
 253 measured at 4.67 V vs Na^+/Na . The resulting pattern contains peaks corresponding to α ,
 254 β , and δ phases (Figure S6; Tables S3–S6 - note that given the large number of refined
 255 parameters, these values should be taken as indicative), as the data measured
 256 correspond to a galvanostatic experiment that was carried out at high current density.
 257 Note that the γ phase is not observed, probably due to the higher current density
 258 applied, because this phase is only observed in a very narrow voltage range ($\Delta V = 0.17$
 259 V) in the operando XRD experiment. However, the data can be used to determine the

260 Na occupancy of each of the observed phases and therefore elucidate the Na⁺
261 deintercalation sequence upon the first charge process (Table 1).

262 Table 1. Na⁺-Refined Occupancies in α , β , and δ Phases in the NCP-C Sample Obtained from HRXRD Measured at 4.67
263 V vs Na⁺/Na and Resulting Value of x in Na_{4-x}Co₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇.

	α	β	δ
Occ Na1	0.82(2)	0.66(8)	0.23(1)
Occ Na2	1.0	1.0	0.63(1)
Occ Na3	1.0	1.0	0.64(1)
Occ Na4	0.68(1)	0.28(8)	0.0
x in Na _{4-x} Co ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ P ₂ O ₇	3.5	2.94	1.5

264 At 4.67 V vs Na⁺/Na, the α phase contains approximately 5/6 of Na1 and 2/3 of Na4,
265 while Na2 and Na3 remain fully occupied (Na_{3.5}Co₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇). The β phase corresponds
266 to a material with 2/3 of Na1 and around 1/3 of Na4, in addition to Na2 and Na3,
267 resulting in a composition of Na_{2.94}Co₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇. In contrast, only 1/4 of Na1, and 2/3
268 of Na2 and Na3 remain in the structure of the δ phase, leading to a composition close
269 to Na_{1.5}Co₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇. The refined composition of the α phase correlates remarkably
270 well with the corresponding Na concentration of the operando XRD experiment at the
271 end of the solid solution process involving the α phase (Figure 4). For β and δ phases the
272 Na concentration differs slightly, most probably because of the fact that these phases
273 appear concomitant to electrolyte decomposition (above 4.3 V vs Na⁺/Na)⁴⁰ and to the
274 higher current density used. It can thus be concluded that the Na⁺ extraction sequence
275 starts with Na4 which progressively leaves the structure until it has been emptied in the
276 δ phase, while Na1 is simultaneously removed, although at a lower rate as 1/4 remains in
277 the structure in the δ phase. In turn, Na2 and Na3 start leaving the structure
278 simultaneously at certain Na⁺ content but are still partially occupied in the δ phase.
279 Therefore, this result indicates that Na⁺ are sequentially extracted, and partial
280 occupancies are found. No superstructure peaks could be observed in the collected
281 HRXRD pattern, although the existence of specific Na⁺/vacancy configurations cannot be
282 discarded in view of the refined compositions. Longer measurement times would be
283 needed to detect any low-intensity superstructure peaks. Moreover, the determined
284 Na⁺ extraction sequence is supported by the calculated diffusion path by the bond
285 valence energy landscape (BVEL) approach, shown in Figure 6. NCP-C is found to exhibit
286 2D Na⁺ diffusion, with a diffusion path that is roughly along a through the connection of
287 all types of Na (Figure 6a), and another path roughly along b involving only Na4 (Figure
288 6b). Both calculated and experimental data thus confirm that all four Na participate in
289 the redox reaction.

290 Figure 6. BVEL map of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ viewed along (a) b and (b) a. Isosurface level $E - E_{\text{min}} = 1.05$ eV and $E - E_{\text{min}} = 0.82$ eV, respectively. $[\text{CoO}_6]$ and $[\text{PO}_4]$ polyhedral are represented in grey, Na atoms, in green, O in red, Co in purple, and P in pink. The blue volumes represent the diffusion path.

294 During the discharge process, NCP-C follows the same phase sequence except for an
 295 additional ϵ' phase, whose cell parameters would lie between those of the ϵ and δ
 296 phases. The ϵ' phase was not observed upon charge; however, the corresponding
 297 oxidation peak in the dQ/dV plot at the end of the first charge process clearly exhibits
 298 splitting. This splitting could correspond to a redox process associated to such a phase,
 299 which might not have been detected in the XRD data. On the other hand, the different
 300 kinetics of the discharge process also results in a slightly different sequence of redox
 301 processes (e.g., a solid-solution region appears now for both δ and β phases at the
 302 expense or shortening of other processes). The different reaction path upon charge and
 303 discharge processes has been already shown in other polyanionic compounds.^{22,41,42}
 304 Finally, the β phase does not completely transform into the α phase and therefore a
 305 biphasic region is observed during the end of discharge (Figure S7). Moreover, cell
 306 parameters indicate that the α phase is not recovered at the end of the discharge, as the
 307 (200) reflection never returns to the initial 2θ values, possibly because of the incomplete
 308 insertion on the Na1 and Na4 sites. This new phase has been labeled as the α' phase,
 309 with similar b and c cell parameters as the α phase but a smaller a cell parameter ($a =$
 310 $17.646(1)$ Å at 4.00 V vs Na^+/Na after the first cycle). The second charge process follows
 311 the same peak evolution as the first charge but with initial composition as α' and a small
 312 amount of the β phase (Figure S8).

313 The structural evolution of NCP-C elucidated here differs with respect to the
 314 isostructural Fe- and Ni-based compounds (single-phase reaction over the whole voltage
 315 range). However, similarities can be found with the Mn-based compound, even though
 316 the cell parameter evolution is different. The Mn compound undergoes a contraction of
 317 a and b cell parameters and the expansion of c during the charge process, while all cell
 318 parameters are reduced in $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. This can be attributed to the local

319 structure changes around Na vacancies that distort the $[\text{CoO}_6]$ octahedra, as calculated
320 by DFT.³⁸ The differences in the order of Na^+ extraction can be responsible for the
321 different structural and cell parameter evolution. Interestingly, the NCP-C sample
322 follows similar Na^+ extraction sequence as the Ni-based compound.²⁴ Figure 7a,b show
323 the Nyquist plots of the experimental data and the calculated fit corresponding to the
324 first charge and discharge of Figure 5. The resistance values shown in Figure 5d have
325 been determined by fitting the impedance data with the equivalent circuit described in
326 the Experimental Section. All EIS data show two semicircles, one at HF region (above 3
327 kHz) and another one at MF (between 3 kHz and 6 Hz), in addition to a straight line at LF
328 (below 6 Hz). The HF semicircle is assigned to the Na^+ migration through the SPI layer,
329 the semicircle at MF corresponds to the charge-transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and the straight
330 line to the Na^+ solid-state diffusion. The semicircle at HF assigned to the SPI layer
331 resistance (R_{SPI}) increases from 14 to 18 Ω upon charge. At the beginning of discharge, it
332 continues increasing until 4.5 V vs Na^+/Na , reaching 22 Ω , and then remains constant.
333 This suggests that the SPI layer grows until it completely forms and then it remains
334 stable. Its formation is concomitant to the phase evolution from the α to the γ phase.
335 The fact that the initial R_{SPI} value is already considerable at 4.0 V can be attributed to
336 the SPI layer forming once the cell is assembled and before a voltage is applied
337 presumably from the NaPF_6 , EC, and DEC decomposition reactions when they are in
338 contact with metallic Na in half-cells.⁴³ R_{CT} increases more significantly, from 15 to 39 Ω
339 in the α phase region. However, after R_{CT} reaches the maximum value (39 Ω) at 4.14 V
340 vs Na^+/Na (which corresponds to around 0.15 Na^+ extracted) R_{CT} decreases and reaches
341 its minimum value (3.5 Ω) when the β phase appears (4.34 V). This suggests that an
342 activation energy has to be overcome to remove the initial Na^+ but at higher voltage the
343 extraction is faster. Interestingly, the removal of 0.18 Na^+ in the α phase is close to the
344 extracted Na^+ amount at the maximum R_{CT} value; suggesting that Na^+ deintercalation
345 could be a major component of the highest R_{CT} . In the successive structural transitions
346 observed by operando XRD the obtained R_{CT} values are very low (<7 Ω) varying only 2%
347 between the highest and lowest R_{CT} value. This is indicative of the fact that, although
348 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ shows numerous phase transitions, these do not affect transport
349 properties, resulting in a material with high structural stability, in agreement with the
350 excellent capacity retention observed.

351
 352 Figure 7. Correlative operando EIS data of the NCP-C sample. Nyquist plots in the frequency range of 5 mHz to 100
 353 kHz upon (a) charge and (b) discharge processes. During charge α (4.00–4.31 V), $\alpha + \beta$ (4.34–4.39 V), $\beta + \gamma$ (4.42–4.45
 354 V), γ (4.48 V), $\gamma + \delta$ (4.50–4.56 V), $\delta + \epsilon$ (4.59 V) and ϵ (4.61–4.70 V) phase evolution, while during discharge ϵ
 355 (4.70–4.56 V), $\epsilon + \epsilon' + \delta$ (4.53–4.50 V), δ (4.48 V), $\delta + \gamma$ (4.45 V), γ (4.42–4.36 V), $\gamma + \beta$ (4.34–4.31 V), β (4.28–4.14 V)
 356 and $\beta + \alpha'$ (4.11–4.00 V) (V vs Na^+/Na).

357 During the discharge process, between 4.7 and 4.48 V (until the δ phase is developed),
 358 R_{CT} values are constant and low because of the expected “easy” Na_2 and Na_3 insertion,
 359 as suggested by HRXRD. However, after 4.48 V (at which Na_1 insertion occurs), R_{CT}
 360 increases gradually indicating that the β phase transformation is kinetically more
 361 sluggish, also in agreement with the higher polarization observed at the end of discharge
 362 in the galvanostatic profile of Figure 3. Finally, at the end of the discharge, close to 4.12
 363 V (where Na_4 and a small amount of Na_1 should be inserted), R_{CT} reaches a similar value
 364 to that of the beginning of the charge process (15 Ω). It does not, however, reach the
 365 maximum observed at 4.14 V vs Na^+/Na during the first charge process, as the β phase
 366 is not completely transformed into the α phase, but partially to α' . Indeed, the absence
 367 of the R_{CT} increment in the second charge process (Figure S9) is in agreement with the
 368 fact that a small amount of Na_1 was not reinserted; leading to an initial composition of
 369 $\text{Na}_{\sim 3.1}\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in the following cycles. Even so, the incomplete Na^+ intercalation
 370 during the first discharge process appears to be beneficial for the cycling stability and
 371 kinetics. This is confirmed by the fact that in the following cycle R_{CT} values do not
 372 significantly increase unlike the first charge and therefore an activation energy is only
 373 required in the first cycle. Such R_{CT} values are, to the best of our knowledge, the lowest
 374 values reported for a Na-based cathode material (even lower than Fe-based analogue).³⁹

375 CONCLUSIONS

376 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ exhibits good electrochemical performance with >95% capacity
377 retention when CBP is used as a carbon precursor. The structural evolution of
378 $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ exhibits a complex reaction mechanism, which consists of four
379 biphasic regions followed by a solid-solution region at the highest voltage. The structural
380 evolution is not completely reversible in the first cycle, but is found to be beneficial in
381 view of the transport properties and cycling stability; because the irreversibility avoids
382 a huge increment on the charge-transfer resistance that is observed in the initial charge.
383 The correlative EIS data show that the transport properties of NCP-C are not significantly
384 affected by the complex structural evolution of $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ and corroborate the
385 ease of Na^+ deintercalation/intercalation, which in turn is reflected in the excellent
386 capacity retention. The correlative operando XRD and EIS experiment presented here
387 shows that the combination of both these techniques can provide a comprehensive
388 foundation about structural and transport properties under real dynamic conditions.
389 Such an experiment represents a relevant advance to fully understand the real operation
390 mechanism of this and other Na-ion materials.

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